

Optimization of Thermoelectric Properties of Carbon nanotube (CNT) veils by Defect Engineering

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1 Introduction

Thermoelectrics(TE) for Energy Conversion

Seebeck effect (Heat energy to electrical energy)

Model of TE Generator (π -Type)

1 Introduction

TE Performance of Materials

Evaluation of Thermoelectric Performance of Materials

- Thermoelectric Figure-of-merit

$$ZT = \frac{S^2 \sigma}{\kappa} T$$

S : Seebeck coefficient

σ : Electric conductivity

T : Absolute temperature

κ : Thermal conductivity

Requirement for practical applications: $ZT = 1$

- Power Factor

$$PF = S^2 \sigma$$

high ZT

→ **high efficiency**

→ **application**

1 Introduction

Organic thermoelectric materials

Nano Energy 102, 107678 (2022)

Nature communications, 1, 1-8 (2020)

Macromol. Res. 28(6), 531-552 (2020)

Advantages

Flexible

Easy processing

Scalable

Non-toxic

1 Introduction

Adv. Funct. Mater., 32, 2203080 (2022)

Nano Energy 89 (2021) 106487

Nature communications, 8, 1-9 (2017)

- Thermoelectric Figure-of-merit

$$ZT = \frac{S^2 \sigma}{\kappa} T$$

1 Introduction

- Core:**
- Silicon
 - Gold
 - Glass
 - Silk
 - Ice
 - Germanium
 - Polystyrene
 - Biodegradable polymers
 - Monolayer graphene

- Polymer cladding:**
- Polysulfone (PSf)
 - Polyethersulfone (PES)
 - Polycarbonate (PC)
 - Polyetherimide (PEI)
 - Cyclic olefin polymer (COP)
 - Poly (methyl methacrylate) (PMMA)

Nature, 534, 529–533 (2016)

Matter 2, 666–679 (2020)

1 Introduction

Nature, 534, 529–533 (2016)

Core fragments can be self-healed/reconnected by thermal treatment

2 Scheme

Illustration of the fabrication and stretching treatment of PC/CNT/PC composites

3 Results and Discussion

□ Mechanical properties at 160 °C

PC film

CNT veil

PC/CNT/PC composite

Load speed of 100 % min⁻¹ was chosen for the PC/CNT/PC composites. For PC/CNT/PC, the maximum draw ratio (DR) can reach about 3.

Draw ratio is defined as the ratio between the final length and the original length.

□ Stretching and heat-repaired results

Initial

Stretched

Heat-repaired

DR=1.5

DR=1.75

DR=2

Microscope images of PC/CNT/PC composites

PC/CNT/PC can almost be repaired by thermal treatment and the critical fragment length is about $300 \mu\text{m}$.

□ Microstructures of heat-repaired CNT veils

The SEM results show the thermal treatment can reconnect CNT veil fragments electrically but not thermally.

TE performance of PC/CNT/PC composites

With the increase of DR, the electrical conductivity decreases, while the Seebeck coefficient increases a little bit.

□ Thermal conductivity of heat-repaired CNT veil

□ Mesoscopic simulations of thermal conductivity of stretched CNT veils

4 Conclusion

- 1 PC/CNT/PC composites can form fragments via solid-state drawing, which can be repaired by thermal treatment.
- 2 A 3.5-fold reduction in thermal conductivity of CNT veils (from 46 to 13 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹) has been achieved, combined with an increase in Seebeck coefficient of 10% and a decrease in electrical conductivity of 26%.
- 3 The maximum estimated ZT is 2.7×10^{-2} for heat-repaired PC/CNT/PC of DR = 1.5.

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